

THE LIFE, SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL ACTIVITIES OF THE FAIR LEADER, ACADEMICIAN KHADICHA SULAIMANOVA

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ABSTRACT

In this article, academician Khadicha Sulaimanova's contribution to the development of science, her efforts to establish a legal country, her meaningful and exemplary life, and her scientific and cultural heritage. Also, the opinions of Khadicha Sulaimanova's contemporaries are mentioned.

Khadicha Sulaimanova, the third of 4 children in the family, was born on July 3, 1913 in Andijan, Turkestan, in the family of father Sulayman and mother Otinoyi. His father, Sulayman Kelganboyev, was an intelligent person who could converse in many languages. He died in the fight against the "printers" who appeared in the Ferghana Valley. Khadicha, who lost her father early, goes to school on the same day as her brother Yusufjan, sister Mo'tabar, and brother Niyoz. Khadicha, who stands out from her peers with her sharp mind and exemplary behavior, graduated from a 9-year Russian school.

Tajikhon Shodiyeva, who participated in the open court hearing regarding the murder of Nurkhan, who was known to the people as an artist by his own brother, was shocked by the sharp speech delivered by Shodiyeva, and saw the solemn courtroom and dignified judges. 17-year-old Khadicha was sitting there, shining, with a burning desire to be like these people. Yes, it was this event that strongly motivated young Khadicha to become interested in law, especially criminal law.

The desire to become a lawyer brings him to the preparatory course of the Institute of Soviet Construction and Legal Research. After studying here for 1 year, Khadija was admitted to the 2nd year of the Faculty of Law at the Institute of Soviet Construction and Law named after Jahan Obidova in Tashkent.

Even in her student years, the future academician Khadicha is quickly recognized among her fellow students with her quick learning and memorization of complex legal concepts and legislation, and she catches the attention of many experienced specialists and teachers and becomes her favorite student. Khadija never stops working on herself and developing. His dream was to become the person he once dreamed of being. He worked as a people's judge for a while, and later as a judge of the Supreme Court. Then he entered the Department of Criminal Law of the Moscow Law Institute as a graduate student. It was a great honor for Khadija that she was noticed and mentored by Traynin, a major criminologist, Correspondent member of

the Academy of Sciences of the SSR, in the first days of her postgraduate studies. Khadicha, who was unable to finish her dissertation because of the war, works first as an assistant, then as an associate professor of the Department of Criminal Law at the Tashkent Law Institute. Along with teaching, Khadicha Sulaimanova works on her unfinished dissertation and on July 20, 1945, she defends her dissertation on "Criminal laws of the Uzbek SSR during the period of military intervention and civil war" at the All-Union Institute of Legal Sciences under the Commissariat of Justice of the SSR. She was the first Uzbek woman to receive a degree in In September 1948, he was sent to the Academy of Sciences of the SSR for a doctoral study for 2 years. During these years, his article "Emergence of the Soviet Criminal Law in Uzbekistan" was published in the magazine "Soviet State and Law". Later, an article titled "History of the Establishment of Soviet Courts in the Uzbek SSR" was published. The defense of Khadicha Sulaimanova's doctoral thesis was a sensational event for the development of the legal system of Turkestan ASSR and Uzbekistan SSR. Because at that time there were only a few women who defended their doctoral dissertations in the field of jurisprudence, and only a few men.

In September 1954, Khadicha Sulaymanova was appointed director of the Tashkent Law Institute. In the same year, he received the honorary title of "Honored Scientist of the Uzbek SSR".

"Khadicha Sulaimanova was a very cheerful, cheerful woman, she cared about every student. He would give me all the pen fees he received for his published works to keep in a safe and then distribute them to financially needy students. "Khadicha Sulaimanova never spent her pen fee on herself, it was her help to students," said the receptionist Galeyeva L.S.¹

There is information that Khadicha Sulaimanova was one of the leading authors and editors of the first textbook on Soviet criminal law published in Uzbek.²

The Uzbek jurist began working as the Minister of Justice of the Republic in September 1959, and during his leadership period, he paid great attention to strengthening the promotion and clarification of laws. Due to her efforts, the number of female employees in the ministry has increased significantly, and she is involved in the establishment of the Tashkent Forensic Research Institute. Khadicha Sulaimanova paid special attention to the training of qualified scientists. As an example, the first graduate student of Sulaymonova M.S. Vasikova (former Minister of Justice) says: "Professor H.S. Sulaymonova always found time for the work of training scientists, despite being extremely busy. He raised every scientific worker as his own child. He was a gracious, sensitive, pure-hearted person. He worked with the will of his heart without sparing himself."³

Khadicha Sulaimanova's services in the field of law are incomparable. It is one of the painful issues of that time, gender equality, justice and protection of women's rights and freedoms by defending legal reforms that eliminate such barriers. She always proved by her

¹ Feruza, Abdumutaliyeva. "THE FIRST FEMALE UZBEK LAWYER—HADICHA SULAYMANOVA." *Confrencea* 5.05 (2023): 363-366.

² 1 Xadicha Sulaymonova- huquqshunos, olima, davlat arbobi/M. Hakimov, G'. Ahmedov, A. Saidov.-T.:O'zbekiston, 1993.- 41 b

³ Xadicha Sulaymonova- huquqshunos, olima, davlat arbobi/M. Hakimov, G'. Ahmedov, A. Saidov.-T.:O'zbekiston, 1993.- 43 b

example that women and men always have equal rights, that women can use their rights, and that women can work in the field of management.

V. Borisoglebsky, the deputy chairman of the Supreme Court of the USSR, a member of the military collegium, expressed his opinion poetically after the big conference held in Tashkent, and recited the following poem:

JK and JPK are trampling,
Fierce discussion, arguments stopped,
According to the law of the Union
The content is embedded in local law.
The light of knowledge is bright in your heart,
Thirsty hearts enjoy your words
Katta rahmat sizga, olim opajon.
All the meetings with you are good.
Warm kindness, for bread and salt
We bow our heads and bow.
After the meeting is over,
We look forward to seeing you in Moscow.⁴

These lines prove that Khadicha Sulaimanova had a high respect and position among the lawyers of the entire SSR. This poem is a great tribute to Khadicha Sulaimanova, who has become glorious in our memory.

He lived a short life and died when he was full of strength and knowledge. Nevertheless, the talented scientist, the possessor of deep knowledge, Khadichha Sulaymonovna, performed many meritorious works in the republic and made a great contribution to the development of the science of jurisprudence. She was a woman who loved her work more than her life. We will always remember with deep gratitude and respect the wonderful daughter of the Uzbek people, who devoted her life to the development of Soviet jurisprudence, strengthening law and order and legislation in our country. We should learn from his respect for knowledge, his love for his work, and his enthusiasm. We will always be proud of Khadicha Sulaimanova and always remember her.

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⁴ Xadicha Sulaymonova- huquqshunos, olima, davlat arbobi/M. Hakimov, G'. Ahmedov, A. Saidov.-T.:O'zbekiston, 1993.-29b